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**A NEW APPROACH TO PREVENTING ANXIETY AND DEPRESSIVE DISORDERS
IN PATIENTS WITH CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES UNDER PSYCHOSOCIAL
STRESS**

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Annotation. *In their daily work, general practitioners and cardiologists often encounter difficult and urgent clinical situations without special training, additional knowledge and interpretation skills. Psychopathological disorders observed in patients with various diseases of the cardiovascular system (CVS) are characterized by polymorphism of symptoms, differ in their own dynamics or clinical manifestations, which complicates the differential diagnosis, treatment and prevention of cardiovascular pathologies.*

Key words. *Cardiovascular diseases, ischemic heart disease, psychosocial stress, psychogenic factors, depression.*

It is known that the development of coronary atherosclerosis and ischemic heart disease (IHD) is significantly increased due to certain risk factors such as arterial hypertension, dyslipidemia, diabetes, older age, male gender, smoking, lack of physical activity, overweight, alcohol dependence. Psychosocial, psychoemotional stress factors affecting the cardiovascular system and associated psychopathological disorders at the neurotic and affective levels are still common. The general strategy for the prevention, treatment and prognosis of socially significant cardiovascular diseases (CVD) should be implemented taking into account the individual, medical and social characteristics of the patient [1]. One of the important goals of secondary prevention of ischemic heart disease is to prevent its complications, that is, to achieve it by correcting risk factors and treating underlying diseases of ischemic disease.

Psychosocial stress and negative emotional distress can contribute to the development of psychiatric symptoms and affect the cardiovascular system. The presence of moderate to severe depression is associated with an increased risk of myocardial infarction and death from ischemic heart disease, as well as a poorer prognosis after acute coronary syndrome. Clinically significant anxiety and anxiety disorders are common in patients with cardiovascular disease, but research in this area is limited. Anxiety disorders, including panic disorder, complicate the course of CAD.

In the mechanisms of psychotraumatic influence, vegetative hyperactivity of the sympathetic adrenal system and neuroendocrine dysfunctions play an important role [2]. In this regard, psychoemotional stress is a set of psychological, physiological and behavioral reactions of a person. What distinguishes a cardiologist patient with complex and painful somatic and mental pathology in the clinical picture of his illness? First of all, this patient needs the help of not only a cardiologist or therapist, but also a psychiatrist and psychotherapist [3]. In this regard, there is a need to determine what place psychological characteristics and psychopathological manifestations occupy in the structure of his illness.

Cardiovascular diseases and psychosocial stress. An analysis of psychotraumatic experience with individual assessment was carried out. The significance of psychogenic factors (stressors) was assessed in 86 people (male/female 42/44) with significant mental disorders of the neurotic and affective levels and specific cardiovascular diseases. The study was conducted on the basis of the SHGBSMP. Of these, 31 patients with cardiovascular diseases and ischemic heart disease (age 53.17 ± 7.25 years) and 55 patients with arterial hypertension (45.55 ± 9.41 years) who were previously under the supervision of a cardiologist or therapist were studied. During hospitalization in the emergency department, psychopathological symptoms prevailed in the clinical picture of patients with cardiovascular pathology, which led to their referral to a psychiatrist.

Among the most significant, strong psychotraumatic factors, there were work-related stress, bereavement, and medical problems, which were particularly important for men (50% of men versus 37% of women). Major life events, family conflicts, and negative interpersonal relationships were relevant for 61.8% of women and 49.1% of men. These results indicate the important role of psychosocial factors in the development of cardiovascular disorders.

Multivariate analysis revealed that the age of onset of ischemic heart disease in the general group was 50.1 ± 7.0 years, while the age of onset of mental disorders was 47.3 ± 8.4 years. The age of onset of ischemic heart disease was 54.2 ± 5.6 years in 11 women and 48.3 ± 6.8 years in 20 men ($p=0.0232$). A relationship was found between the age of onset of mental disorders and the functional class of angina ($p=0.0001$) and the gender of the patients ($p=0.0007$). The diagnosis of ischemic heart disease was “delayed” in patients with a predominant clinical picture of anxiety, depression, asthenia, etc. psychopathological manifestations [4]. In such cases, ischemic heart disease was diagnosed at the stage of an already established clinical picture or the development of acute coronary syndrome (fatal myocardial infarction). In this regard, in patients with coronary artery disease with neurotic and affective disorders, the periods before the initial diagnosis of ischemic heart disease or its exacerbation, the development of unstable angina, acute coronary syndrome were characterized by significant psychotraumatic events (psychosocial stress). The occurrence of mental disorders in patients with arterial hypertension: regularities related to the duration and time of manifestation of patients and the traumatic effect of stress factors were established. The initial stage of arterial hypertension coincides with the appearance of psychopathological disorders of a predominantly neurotic level, caused by the influence of psychosocial factors (anxiety-phobic disorders, severe depression, adjustment disorders, somatoform disorders, neurasthenia). These changes are determined in the development of stage I of arterial hypertension. In the more severe course of stage II-III of arterial hypertension, psychostressors and the associated affective (depressive) and neurotic disorders act as a provoking factor in the clinic and exacerbation of previously detected hypertension. The incidence of hypertension in patients with neurotic and affective disorders was 68.4%. Psychosocial stress factors contribute to the development of hypertension, and the duration of exposure plays an important role.

Blood lipids and depressive disorders. Regardless of the nosological nature of the mental state, the clinical picture of patients with ischemic heart disease, in which depressive disorders predominate, is aggravated by both symptoms of depression (depressed mood, anergy, weakness, anhedonia, insomnia, tearfulness) and symptoms of cardiovascular disease [5].

Multivariate analysis of variance revealed a significant relationship between the level of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) fraction and the leading depressive syndrome, neurotic and

affective disorders ($p = 0.0083$), as well as the functional class of heart failure ($p = 0.0116$). Patients with affective disorders had the highest levels of total cholesterol (TC) and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol fraction in the blood serum, as well as a tendency to decrease high-density lipoprotein cholesterol. Clinically, the identified changes in blood lipids were observed in patients with angina pectoris class III that developed after psychotraumatic stress.

The results of the study suggest that stress factors and associated psychiatric disorders of the depressive spectrum contribute to the long-term course and exacerbation of CAD. In patients with ischemic heart disease, patients with comorbid neurotic disorders with anxiety syndrome (i.e., phobic and anxiety disorders: agoraphobia, panic disorder, generalized anxiety disorder, mixed anxiety and depressive disorder), the average level of high-density lipoprotein cholesterol did not exceed 0.98 mmol/l, and the level of triglycerides (TG) was very high.

In the group of patients with ischemic heart disease with anxiety-phobic and anxiety-depressive manifestations, the clinical symptoms differed significantly. The main indicators of patients' appeal to a psychiatrist were: complaints of decreased activity, decreased ability to work, depressive mood due to attacks of fear of death (myocardial infarction, stroke). Panic attacks ("all-encompassing fear"), which occur suddenly and are not limited to a specific situation, are accompanied by fear of death, anxiety about one's own health, the appearance of pain, pressure in the heart, a feeling of inadequacy, anxiety about "expecting" attacks with the development of air, blood pressure, vegetative manifestations, neurotic fixation and hypochondriacal changes, depressive mood, passive suicidal thoughts [6]. Cardiophobic syndrome is very important in men and women, since with the development of ischemic heart disease, patients with panic disorder develop thanatophobic syndrome (fear of death). Psychoemotional disorders play a large role in the occurrence of angina attacks, emotional stress is associated with pain and vegetative phenomena. In this regard, in patients with neurotic and affective disorders, ischemic heart disease can occur for some time without obvious symptoms of angina syndrome and even asymptotically. Clinical equivalents of IHD are symptoms of a somatovegetative and psychological nature, which complicates the initial diagnosis. In such cases, it is necessary to pay attention to the differential diagnostic difficulties in recognizing cardiovascular diseases. What is the reason for the underrecognition of IHD? The first clinical signs of the disease appear during the stages of decompensation of psychopathological disorders, which is the impetus for patients to seek treatment.

The predominance of depressive and anxiety disorders in the clinical picture masks the symptoms of IHD. In addition, the leading psychopathological syndromes include paroxysms of fear, algia of other localizations, dysphagia, difficulty breathing, skin paresthesia. The nature of the pain, the lack of a clear connection between an anginal attack and physical activity, the unclear localization of pain, the lack of antianginal effect of nitroglycerin, the relief of paroxysms and cardiac pain by taking tranquilizers or antidepressants usually raise doubts about the presence of ischemic heart disease and give reason to consider these manifestations as "anginoid syndrome" [7]. In such cases, the clinical symptoms of IHD, which have developed on the basis of severe psychopathological disorders, are often not noticed by the patient himself and may be incorrectly recognized by a general practitioner or cardiologist during the periods of observation of patients in general somatic treatment and prevention institutions.

The abundance and diversity of cardiac and extracardiac changes and phenomena associated with psychoemotional stress initially complicates the diagnosis of ischemic heart disease.

Psychopathological disorders in cardiovascular diseases are difficult to diagnose in both psychiatric and general medical practice, and are also a serious problem for the patient himself. It is necessary to understand the concept of risk factors. Step analysis allows us to identify not only a set of known risk factors for cardiovascular pathology (dyslipidemia, arterial hypertension, heart rhythm disorders, diabetes or impaired glucose tolerance, obesity, changes in the vessels of the fundus, family heredity of heart disease and other indicators), but also predictors that assess the mental and psychosocial state of the patient [8]. Particular attention should be paid to such indicators of psychosocial significance as the period of onset of mental disorders, the diagnosis of mental disorders

(neurotic and affective level), the psychological characteristics of patients (high levels of anxiety with paroxysms of dissatisfaction with their situation, guilt, fear of death).

The examination plan for patients with a predominant clinical picture of anxiety and/or depressive disorders should include a study of the blood lipid spectrum and laboratory and instrumental diagnostic methods for early detection of ischemic heart disease (in men over 40 years of age). The ability of an internist (therapist, general practitioner, cardiologist) to quickly identify and diagnose psychopathological disorders in general medical practice, which requires improving their knowledge of psychosomatic medicine, is no less important. Patients with anxiety and depressive disorders and dyslipidemia constitute a group at high risk of developing and complicating cardiovascular diseases. It is necessary to consider these psychosocial risk factors (along with other risk factors) as indicators of the degree of stratification of the development of complications of cardiovascular pathology and the risk of their prognosis as a whole. This allows for the development of rehabilitation programs for patients with cardiovascular diseases associated with mental disorders and the search for a promising approach to integrative multifactorial prevention with coordinated interaction of therapeutic and psychiatric specialists.

Principles of treatment of comorbid diseases. The frequency of anxiety and depressive disorders of the neurotic system at the affective level in patients with cardiovascular diseases, primarily in the provision of complex medical care, forces doctors to pay special attention to the importance of these factors. General principles of treatment of patients with comorbid somatic and mental disorders include the addition and correction of psychotropic therapy to the classical treatment regimen for coronary artery disease and hypertension [9]. The main goal of pharmacotherapy is the reduction of psychopathological disorders, improvement of the somatic condition of patients and restoration of normal functions of patients.

Anxiolytics are widely used in the treatment of cardiovascular diseases, which require correction of somatovegetative, psychovegetative and psychopathological symptoms, as well as anxiety disorders.

The most effective non-benzodiazepine anxiolytic - afobazole - is a drug that is effective against anxiety, panic attacks. Afobazole is a selective anxiolytic drug with a hypnosedative effect. Afobazole was prescribed to 22 patients (mean age - 43.4 ± 5.2) with a diagnosis of essential arterial hypertension of the I-II degree and neurotic mental states with anxiety syndrome and stress disorders. The effectiveness of treatment with afobazole was assessed for 4 weeks at a dose of 30 mg/day. Patients with hypertension with anxiety syndrome were prescribed afobazole in combination with antihypertensive drugs (ACE inhibitors, diuretics, β -adrenoblockers, etc.). Afobazole at a dose of 30 mg/day. showed a pronounced anti-anxiety effect, manifested by psychoemotional neurovegetative and somatic anxiety, which restored the normal functioning of patients with hypertension. In patients taking Afobazole, symptoms such as mental depression, drowsiness, and muscle weakness disappeared. In the treatment of patients with hypertension, individual appointment of antihypertensive and antianginal drugs for each patient, availability of drugs, and assessment of their effectiveness are very important. The requirements of modern effective treatment include self-control, compliance with the rules, and adaptation of patients, which, in some cases, may not be effective without the help of a psychotherapist. In general medical practice, the competence of a doctor who promptly identifies psychopathological disorders manifested by anxiety and fear is of great importance, that is, they will be able to improve their skills in psychosomatic medicine [10].

Thus, the search for an optimal approach to diagnostics, complex somatic treatment and psychopharmacotherapy, and the assessment of the effectiveness and efficiency of this treatment are guided by the requirements of practical medicine. "You cannot look at the patient through a narrow window. The body is a whole being, and it is necessary to pay attention to it, that is, to the patient, his difficult worldview, full of doubts and emotions." The most important thing is that when treating each patient, we must not look at him only as an object of our profession, but rather, we must not forget that the human body is a large system, paying attention to his inner world, his state of mind. In addition, the quality of treatment depends on the patient's behavior, his ability to quickly get used to

the treatment regimen, and to take the prescribed medications without interruption, in other words, the doctor needs the help of a psychotherapist.

The neurobiology underlying the relationship between stress and CVD has only begun to emerge, but it already provides fertile ground for future research. Prospective studies should be performed to evaluate the roles of additional candidate mediating factors in the mechanistic pathway, including SNS activity and glucocorticoid levels, and to assess the efficacy of pharmacologic and non-pharmacologic therapies targeting components of this mechanism, taking into consideration potential confounders such as substance use, diet, and physical activity. Further, investigations into the relationship between upstream factors that contribute to psychosocial stress and amygdalar activity, such as socioeconomic status and environmental conditions, should be performed. The relationship between amygdalar activity and other downstream manifestations of CVD should be examined. Additionally, it is important to evaluate the roles of other neural centers involved in the response to stress (e.g., hippocampus, hypothalamus, prefrontal cortex, insula) in this mechanism. Given limitations in the direct measurement of perceived stress in current clinical practice, the role of amygdalar activity as a quantifiable and potentially modifiable proxy measure of perceived stress should be investigated. Finally, the impact of genetic and neurobiological factors in determining an individual's resilience and susceptibility to disease consequent to psychosocial stress merits investigation. The answers to these important questions should further inform our understanding of the relationship between stress and CVD and provide opportunities to improve clinical care.

Psychosocial stress is an unavoidable consequence of daily human life that associates with an increased risk for CVD events that is on par with the risk from traditional CVD risk factors. The CVD consequences of stress ultimately depend upon its degree and duration, as well as on individual differences in responses to a stressor. Recent identification of a neurobiological mechanism in humans that bridges the gap from psychosocial stress to CVD identifies multiple novel interventions, such as anti-inflammatory medications and stress reduction with potentially high impact for preventing and treating the adverse CVD effects of stress. Furthermore, these findings take the next step towards demonstrating a causal relationship between psychosocial stress and CVD and facilitating the broad inclusion of therapies against psychosocial stress in CVD prevention and treatment guidelines [11].

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